

ANALYSIS OF GREETING FORMS IN ORAL SPEECH IN UZBEK AND CHINESE LANGUAGES

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speech etiquette, greetings, politeness, form of address, colloquial and social addresses. Politeness expressions in oral speech in Chinese and Uzbek (礼貌用语, lǐmào yòngyǔ) reflect respect and culture in society. In both languages, there are widely used expressions that demonstrate etiquette and social respect. Below, we will consider some of them

ABSTRACT

Each nation has its own unique language and culture, which reflects the culture of interpersonal relations, especially politeness. Politeness is an integral part of social communication, which is clearly manifested in speech etiquette, forms of address, expressions of gratitude, apologies, and requests. This article analyzes the pragmatic similarities and differences of politeness expressions in Uzbek and Chinese..

Greeting is an important element of speech etiquette, as it serves to establish initial contact, like an address. The rules of greeting etiquette in the Uzbek language have their own distinctive features. The choice of greeting depends on the communicative situation, as well as the age and gender of the interlocutors, and it determines the positive outcome of the interaction. Before becoming acquainted with the various forms of greeting permitted by Uzbek speech etiquette, it should be emphasized that greeting speech is one of the main criteria for recognizing the dignity of the person to whom it is addressed.

Kinesics (bowing the head, making a bow, shaking hands, kissing, patting on the shoulder) and verbal actions (spoken greetings, expressions) are determined not only by objective factors, but also by subjective factors that have influenced the development of a particular people's socio-cultural and ethnographic life.

For people who know each other well (friends, relatives, young people), Uzbek speech etiquette allows such greetings as "Assalomu alaykum" and "Salom." If necessary, and in certain individual situations, a more respectful form may also be used: "Qadamlaringizga hasonot, xush kelibsiz" ("May your steps be blessed, welcome").

In addition, attention should be paid to the words used in greetings that have become firmly established in the speech of young people and adolescents, such as: "Salom!",

“Qalaysan?” (“How are you?”), “Nima gaplar?” (“What’s new?”), and so on. These expressions are not used in formal speech, but they are popular among young people, who actively use them in everyday communication. The expressions “Nima gaplar?” (“What’s new?”) and “Tuzukmisiz?” (“Are you well?”), which are also used during greetings, are widely found in the speech of elderly people with more conservative views.

In Chinese, as in Uzbek, there are many forms of greeting—often impersonal, but they can also take more complex forms by expressing questions or wishes. In China, the most basic form of etiquette is greeting — 打招呼 (dǎ zhāohu). Neutral greeting forms in Chinese include: 你好 (“Hello!”); 您好 (“Hello!” — polite/respectful form); 你们好! (“Hello!” — addressed to a group); 大家好! (“Hello everyone!” — informal, for a group). In no other country in the world is food treated with as much respect and reverence as in China. For this reason, instead of a standard greeting question, Chinese people often ask a food-related question in their interactions: “你好，吃饭了吗?” (“Hello, have you eaten?”). Surprisingly, Chinese people are accustomed to greeting not only each other in this way, but also foreigners and strangers.

In response to such a question, one usually answers: 是，谢谢！你呢？— “Yes, thank you! And you?” Interestingly, Chinese people try to establish contact in this way and hope that you will not respond negatively.

Table 1. Neutral and Culture-Specific Speech Formulas

Expressions	Neutral Speech Expressions	Specific Speech Formulas	
		Categories	Examples
Greetings	你好！ 早上好！	Informal greetings among close people of the same age	嗨 hi (inglizcha) 我的天，我看见谁了! “Ey Hudoyim, men kimni ko'ryapman!” Oh my God, who do I see. 生活怎么样 “hayotingiz qalay?” How is your life 家人怎么样 “uydagilar yaxshimi?” How is your family 有什么新闻 “nima yangiliklar?” What’s new?
		Greeting acquaintances (not very close)	早上好！ “Hayrli tong!” Good morning. 晚上好！ “Hayrli kech!” Good evening. 去哪儿？ “qayerga ketyapsan?” Where are you going. 干啥去？ “nima qilyapsan?” What are

			<p>you going to do. 你吃了吗? “ovqatlandingmi?” Have you eaten.</p>
		Greeting family members	<p>您好, 伯伯好! “Salom amaki” (katta)“Hello, uncle (elder)” 您好, 叔叔 “Salom amaki (kichik)”Hello, uncle (younger)” 你好, 大舅 “Salom tog’a (katta)”Hello, elder uncle (mother’s side)” 阿姨好 “Salom xola(universal) ”Hello, aunt! (universal form) 您好, 姨妈好 “Salom xola Hello, aunt (maternal)”</p>
		Rasmiy muhitda salomlashish: muzokaralar vaqtida salomlashish	<p>您好! Salom!Hello! (polite) 大家好! Barchaga salom! Hello everyone 很高兴有机会与您会面! Siz bilan uchrashishga imkon bo’lganidan xursandman! I am pleased to have the opportunity to meet you!” 热烈欢迎 qarshi olamiz, marhamat! Warm welcome! 我代表 ... 欢迎大家 Ruxsat bersangiz, ... nomidan salom aytmqchiman! Allow me to welcome you on behalf of ...”</p>

In addition, in Uzbek hospitality, the host shows great courtesy to the guest. The guest is always invited to take the place of honor, and during the conversation, expressions such as “Please, help yourself,” “Please, take some,” and “Go ahead and eat” are frequently used. For Chinese people, however, this custom may seem unusual, as they might interpret such invitations literally. In Uzbek culture, these expressions are used as a form of politeness and courtesy.

In Chinese culture, on the other hand, a guest does not usually feel embarrassed; if they are hungry, they may choose to eat, and if not, they may politely decline.

References:

1. Begmatov E. Oliy ta'lim tizimida nutq madaniyatining o'rni. –Toshkent:

O'zbekiston, 1999, 38-b

2. Iskandarova Sh.M. O'zbek nutq odatining muloqot shakllari. Filol.fan.nomz....diss.avtoreferat. Samarqand 1993. B-27.

3. 顾曰国 礼貌、语用与文化[A] 文化与交际[M],北京, 外语教学与研究出版社, 1998.

4. 李乾夫, 李鸿昌, 杨更兴, 杨增发. 中国传统文化概论 — 云南大学出版社, 2015.

